

In Search for a Better Life?
Summary Report of the MIGWELL Project

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MIGWELL

Well-being and Migration:
The Hungary – Austria Migration Nexus

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Centre for Empirical Social Research at the Corvinus University of Budapest

Department of Finno-Ugrian Studies, University of Vienna

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Department of Sociology, University of Vienna

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MIGWELL’s website: [LINK](#)

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The Project: Introducing MIGWELL - Structure, Methodology, and Theoretical Framework

“What does happiness mean? Obviously, a person is happy if they are content. Because if they’re not content, then they’re not happy. But of course, you have to set certain boundaries and standards in order to be happy. Because someone who always longs for something they’ll never be able to achieve in their life will never be happy or content. Yet at the same time, people often just pass by the things they have achieved...”

Woman, 45-60, Elderly caregiver, in AT

The core idea of the MIGWELL project was conceived in 2018. The starting point came from leading researchers who took notice of the OECD’s growing calls and publications advocating for the measurement of well-being, aiming to provide an alternative to GDP in policy-making processes. In parallel, the number of Hungarians living in Austria doubled within four years prior to 2018. The gap between Austria and Hungary is among the largest within the EU when it comes to neighbouring countries — not only in terms of income, but also in terms of subjective well-being. Some researchers have even coined the term “Iron Curtain of unhappiness” to describe this phenomenon. But what exactly is subjective well-being? Throughout the project, we followed the OECD’s Guidelines (2013) and applied measurement indicators consistent with international surveys. We interpreted subjective well-being as an umbrella concept, comprising both hedonic (cognitive and affective) and eudaimonic dimensions of well-being.

The relevance of our research lies in the fact that the Hungary–Austria migration axis remains under-researched despite its growing importance. Furthermore, after reviewing studies from around the world, it becomes evident that the relationship between migration and growth in subjective well-being is far from clear-cut. The project’s innovative approach lies in its analytical framework, which examined this migration nexus through the lens of subjective well-being. We explored causal relationships between migration and subjective well-being (using instrumental variables, retrospective evaluations, and propensity score matching), offering insights that go beyond the associative findings of earlier European studies.

Our two main research directions were, firstly, to investigate how subjective well-being influences the intentions to emigrate from Hungary, and secondly, to assess how the subjective well-being of Hungarian migrants changed as a result of relocating to Austria. Thanks to the application of OECD standards, our primary data are comparable with previous surveys such as EU-SILC and the Hungarian Microcensus, providing an almost complete and accurate picture of the living conditions of a still under-analysed group: Hungarians living in Austria (Although Statistics Austria conducts surveys on immigrant populations, Hungarians are not specifically targeted in those assessments).

MIGWELL ran for a total of three and a half years, from February 2022 to July 2025, and involved three institutions: the Institute for Urban and Regional Research at the Austrian Academy of Sciences, the Centre for Empirical Social Research at Corvinus University of Budapest, and the Department of Finno-Ugrian Studies at the University of Vienna. In addition, an international scientific advisory board supported the project. The research was made possible through funding from the National Research, Development and Innovation Office of Hungary and the Austrian Science Fund.

The project employed both quantitative and qualitative approaches. On the qualitative side, we conducted ten narrative interviews, ten cognitive interviews, five expert interviews, and two policy-maker interviews on both the Hungarian and Austrian sides, as well as a joint roundtable discussion. The quantitative analysis was based on secondary analysis of existing data from EU-SILC and the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus, as well as a representative survey of 1,000 people in Hungary, a supplementary survey involving 375 individuals with migration intentions, and a snowball sample-based survey of 310 Hungarian migrants in Austria (who have spent at least one year in Austria).

The Context: Migration Nexus and Well-Being Gap between Austria and Hungary

“I usually say, if someone can’t find work here in Austria, it’s because they don’t want to work — because there are jobs available.”

Man, 45-60, House caretaker, in AT

Since Austria’s full labour market opening to Hungary in 2011, the number of Hungarians living in Austria has grown significantly. By 2024, their population exceeded 100,000, making them the sixth largest foreign-born minority group in the country. While immigration has continued to rise, especially after 2021, this trend is increasingly accompanied by return migration and circular mobility. In fact, in 2024 for every 100 Hungarians leaving to Austria, 67 returned, reflecting a dynamic and fluid migratory pattern. Geographically, a noticeable shift is underway. Although Vienna and Burgenland have historically been the primary destinations for Hungarian migrants, their relative importance is declining. Instead, the western provinces such as Tyrol and Salzburg are attracting more Hungarians, many of whom are settling in smaller towns with populations of 3,000 to 5,000 and finding employment in the hospitality sector.

Our insights are based on a snowball sampling method among Hungarians in Austria. While this approach limits representativeness, the data align closely with the Austrian-resident sample from Hungary’s 2016 Microcensus. The only notable bias appears to be the overrepresentation of highly educated individuals. When asked about their reasons for migration, financial motives clearly dominate. For 57.5% of respondents, this was among the top three reasons for moving to Austria. A more predictable future and better working conditions were also cited frequently, each appearing in over 35% of responses. Interestingly, these same three factors were also the most commonly cited reasons for wanting to stay in Austria, highlighting their ongoing relevance in migrants’ lives.

On average, Austrian wages are 2.3 times higher than Hungarian wages when adjusted for purchasing power. However, there is a caveat: migrants from post-2004 EU accession countries earn, on average, only about 70% of native Austrians’ income. A secondary analysis of EU-SILC data reveals that Austria offers objectively better living conditions, including lower rates of relative deprivation, better health outcomes, reduced social exclusion, more frequent social interactions, and greater access to leisure activities. In most of these domains, Hungarians in Austria approach or even exceed (e.g. the capability to afford at least one vacation per year) the Austrian scores. However, in some areas, they fare worse than both Austrians and Hungarians in Hungary, especially in perceived social exclusion.

In Hungary, life satisfaction, a key indicator of cognitive subjective well-being, has shown a steady increase since 2013. In our 2024 survey, Hungarians in Austria reported an average life

satisfaction score of 7.4, which falls between the 2022 Austrian average of 7.9 and Hungary's 2024 score of 7.0. This general pattern is mirrored in satisfaction across various life domains. One notable exception is income satisfaction, where Hungarians in Austria report higher levels than the Austrian average. On the other hand, they report lower satisfaction than their counterparts in Hungary in areas such as housing, social relationships, and work-life balance.

A striking duality emerges in affective well-being. Hungarians in Austria report experiencing both positive emotions (e.g., happiness, calmness) and negative ones (e.g., stress, loneliness) more frequently than Hungarians living in Hungary. However, in the domain of eudaimonic well-being, particularly in measures such as optimism (+1.3), they clearly outperform.

Hungarians in Austria maintain strong transnational ties, facilitated by the countries' geographic proximity. In practice, many migrants never truly "leave" Hungary nor fully "arrive" in Austria. They live simultaneously in two social spheres. Over half (54%) visit Hungary at least 4–5 times a year, and nearly half (47%) regularly send money home, indicating a high level of ongoing cross-border engagement.

Migration intentions in Hungary and subjective well-being

“Before migration, I went through a divorce. Three kids, 50% child support. Now, it's easy to add up how much money is needed for someone to get by in a situation like that, and there was no other option. [...] I used to be the kind of person who said, ‘If everyone leaves Hungary, I'll be the last one to close the door, and from the inside.’ I had no intention of going anywhere. But eventually, there was just no other option, no other path.”

Man, 45-60, Waiter, in AT

In our project we explored migration intentions among the Hungarian population using a three-tiered approach (willingness, thought, planning to move abroad within the next two years). For the purposes of this summary, we focus on the most concrete of these: the intention to migrate within two years. Previous Hungarian studies have shown that such concrete plans are statistically significant predictors of actual migration. According to research by Gödri and Feleki (2017), 17% of those with definite plans followed through within three years.

Based on our nationally representative survey of Hungarians aged 18–64, 8.3% plan to emigrate, remarkably similar to the figure recorded in the 2016 Hungarian Microcensus. However, just 14% of this group say they have already made a firm decision to leave. The most commonly cited motivations are financial reasons (83%), a more predictable future, and improved working conditions. Notably, 29% also cited the intention to use migration as a means of improving their long-term prospects in Hungary itself. The majority of potential migrants envision staying abroad for two to five years, but 28% are prepared to leave Hungary permanently. Austria emerged as the most popular destination, named by 43% of those considering emigration. It is followed by Germany, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands. Migration is overwhelmingly driven by employment opportunities, 99% of potential migrants cited work as their primary reason, while only 7% mentioned studying abroad. Migration decisions are largely supported by social networks: while 38% would embark on this journey alone, most enjoy encouragement from family and friends.

The demographic profile of potential migrants aligns with international trends and earlier Hungarian findings. They tend to be younger, more likely to be male, in good health, highly educated, employed, and urban residents. They also have greater access to migration networks, nearly 15% have lived abroad before, and over 80% have relatives or friends already living abroad. As expected, potential migrants hold more favourable views of emigration in general. An overwhelming 99% disagree with the notion that leaving the country amounts to letting it down, a stark contrast to only 71% among those who intend to stay.

A lower level of life satisfaction characterizes those planning to emigrate. Their average life satisfaction score is 6.9, compared to 7.2 among those intending to stay in Hungary. The most pronounced dissatisfaction is seen in time use (a 0.9-point gap) and income satisfaction (a 0.8-

point gap). The latter is particularly noteworthy: although potential migrants are not overrepresented among Hungary's poorest residents, they are concentrated in the middle-income range of 200,000–500,000 HUF per month. Health is the only life domain in which potential migrants report significantly higher satisfaction, a phenomenon consistent with the well-documented "healthy migrant effect." A nuanced pattern emerges when comparing affective and eudaimonic well-being indicators. Potential migrants report more favourable outcomes in affective domains, both positive and negative. In contrast, their scores on eudaimonic indicators, related to meaning, purpose, and long-term psychological flourishing, tend to be lower than those who wish to remain in Hungary.

Our findings based on causal methods confirm a clear link between subjective well-being and migration intention. Lower life satisfaction is one of the factors, which are leading to greater intention to emigrate. More surprisingly, life satisfaction also appears to correlate with where people intend to go. Those planning to move to Austria reported significantly lower levels of satisfaction than those considering other countries, suggesting that Austria, while close and familiar, may attract individuals in particularly acute states of dissatisfaction.

Forms of action potential: Migration propensity and entrepreneurial inclination

“I really admire those who stay in Hungary without being favoured by the current system and still keep fighting. Sometimes I even feel a bit of cowardice in myself. That we left. Well, it is what it is... You only have one life... It often crosses my mind that, even if it’s not treason, it might still be cowardice to run away like this, while someone else stays behind and keeps fighting.”

Man, 30-45, Cashier, in AT

Action potential refers to the readiness and capacity of individuals to respond to changes in their environment. This concept can take different forms: proactive action potential is often expressed through the desire to migrate or start a business, while protest reflects a more reactive, restitutive form of engagement. A third group includes those who remain passive, showing neither proactive nor restitutive tendencies.

In Hungary, nearly one in four adults expresses a desire to live abroad, while around one in seven is considering starting a business. Additionally, close to 30% of respondents say they would be willing to protest if their interests were threatened. Migration and entrepreneurial intentions appear to be strongly connected. People who express a desire to migrate show nearly double the average entrepreneurial inclination. An even stronger association emerges between migration intention and protest potential: almost half of those who consider emigrating are also open to participating in protests.

While gender is not significantly associated with action potential, age plays a more prominent role. Protest inclination does not decline markedly with age, but among younger people, migration intention tends to outweigh protest engagement. A positive self-perception of health also tends to align with proactive action potential, especially migration readiness, which is more frequent among those who report being in excellent health. Family status is another meaningful factor. Single individuals are more likely to express migration, entrepreneurial, and protest inclinations than those with families. Economic activity also matters: about half of students and two-fifths of the unemployed indicate a readiness to migrate, compared to just one in ten pensioners. Migration interest is more prevalent among entrepreneurs and people working outside the public sector. Professional status, entrepreneurial roles, and internal labour market positioning are all positively associated with various forms of action potential.

Migration willingness is notably higher among individuals in both the lower and upper income terciles. For the former group, the motivation may be escape or upward mobility; for the latter, the drive may relate to exploration or opportunity. This V-shaped relationship also characterizes entrepreneurial inclination. However, protest potential does not appear to be strongly linked with income levels. Education tends to be associated with migration and protest tendencies, as well as overall engagement versus passivity, but has less influence on entrepreneurial intention.

Digital connectedness also plays a significant role, especially in relation to migration intentions and overall activity levels. While the connection is somewhat weaker for protest and entrepreneurship, regular internet use still shows a meaningful association with all three. Language skills are particularly influential. Having knowledge of a foreign language correlates strongly with migration intention. The number of languages spoken also shows a general connection with action potential across the board.

Social connectedness contributes as well. People who meet regularly with friends report higher levels of action potential in every category. The frequency of social contact seems more important than either the number of friends or the topics discussed, suggesting that the strength and consistency of close ties matter more than the content of those interactions or the breadth of one's network. Levels of generalized trust appear to be inversely related to migration inclination. People more inclined to migrate tend to report lower trust in others across the board. However, entrepreneurial and protest propensities do not show a significant relationship with trust.

When examining subjective well-being, a V-shaped pattern emerges between affective well-being and both migration and entrepreneurship: people who are either less or more happy than average are more likely to show proactive intentions. Meanwhile, life satisfaction is particularly associated with entrepreneurial inclination, those who are more satisfied are more inclined to start a business. Eudaimonic well-being also reveals interesting associations. The median rating for perceived competence is 8 on a 0-10 scale, indicating that most people feel capable in their daily lives. A strong sense of competence tends to be linked with higher migration interest. A lack of perceived freedom is often associated with a desire to migrate, and entrepreneurial intention again shows a V-shaped connection, more common among those who feel either very constrained or very free. Interestingly, a limited sense of freedom does not appear to align with protest potential, but migration willingness is especially common among those who feel they lack control over how to live their lives.

Drivers of Hungarians' Satisfaction: The Moderating Effect of Country of Residence

“When I came to Austria, I really realized how much I missed Hungarian culture. Because when you're in it, and it's all around you... It's like health, you know... You don't notice it when you have it. When it's gone, that's when you start to appreciate it.”

Woman, 45-60, Nursery teacher, in AT

In the project we have explored how personal, social, and structural factors are related to happiness, life satisfaction, and optimism across different groups (stayers in Hungary, potential migrants from Hungary, and Hungarians living in Austria). Hungarians in Austria often find themselves in a psychological in-between, better off in some ways than those at home, yet also uniquely vulnerable. Their well-being is shaped not only by material conditions but by integration, cultural identity, and the complex dynamics of family and comparison.

One of the most striking revelations is that while factors such as health, income, relationships, and employment universally affect life satisfaction, their weight and meaning vary significantly across contexts and country of current residence. For instance, unemployment exerts a stronger negative impact on well-being among Hungarians in Austria, despite Austria's generous welfare system. We attribute this to guilt, migrants feeling pressure to succeed for the sake of their families back home. Education, typically a strong predictor of life satisfaction in Hungary, does not carry the same weight in Austria, where overqualification and job mismatch may undercut its benefits. Meanwhile, having a partner is associated with increased life satisfaction among stayers and potential migrants, but the effect vanishes among Hungarians living in Austria, where the disadvantage of being single is less prevalent. Perhaps most concerning is the heightened effect of social exclusion in Austria. Among migrants, the negative association between exclusion and life satisfaction is four times stronger than in Hungary. In Hungary, absolute income and material comfort dominate. In Austria, relative income—how one's earnings compare to others—has greater influence, making social comparison a key factor. Similarly, Hungarians in Austria place more value on access to green spaces, public services, and time management, while Hungarians in Hungary remain more tethered to housing, employment, and financial stability based on the correlations between life satisfaction and several domains.

Lack of integration, severed social ties, and distance from cultural roots leave deep psychological imprints. While singles in Austria don't report significantly lower life satisfaction overall, they do experience pronounced deficits in social connection and work satisfaction compared to those in Hungary. Satisfaction with housing, health, and leisure activities also varies by location. Hungarians living in their homeland report greater satisfaction in urban areas, contrary to those who prefer urban density. However, in Austria the urban-rural gap is not significant, in some cases due to the smaller (compared to Hungary) values reported

in urban settings (e.g. social relations), on the other hand due to the larger values observed in rural areas (e.g. health). Financial barriers to leisure significantly lower satisfaction with work-life balance in Austria, more so than in Hungary, highlighting the emotional toll of exclusion from rest and recreation.

Meeting with friends and volunteering are strongly associated with happiness, especially for Hungarians in Austria. Though only 5% belong to Hungarian cultural organizations, interviews stress their value in preserving identity and emotional well-being. Interestingly, higher education is associated with high optimism in Austria but correlates negatively with it in Hungary, suggesting differing expectations and socio-political climates. Yet, despite greater happiness, optimism remains fragile. Potential migrants report 10% more frequent happiness than stayers, but their optimism levels are 8% lower. This split underscores the uncertainty many face. National sentiment is bleak: Potential migrants rate their country's condition just 2.7 out of 10, with war, economic instability, and EU uncertainty shaping a pessimistic outlook.

Postmigrant Perspectives of Subjective Well-Being Among Hungarians in Austria

“When I came here to Austria and things started to normalise a bit, I asked my doctor, ‘Do I really have to take this sedative?’ He said, ‘If you don't feel like you need it, then don't take it!’ I haven't taken a sedative since.”

Man, 45-60, Interior painter, in AT

Is relocating from Hungary to Austria linked with greater life satisfaction? Which areas show noticeable improvement, and where do potential difficulties or declines appear? To explore these questions, we analysed changes in subjective well-being using two methods. First, we asked Hungarian migrants in Austria to reflect on their well-being before moving. This retrospective approach can be challenging, especially for long-term migrants, and may involve subtle self-justification, as people tend to present their past circumstances in less favourable terms to affirm the value of their choice. The second approach applied causal modelling techniques to assess changes in key indicators such as happiness, optimism, life satisfaction, and meaning of life.

The findings offer a compelling picture. Around 70% of migrants reported improved life satisfaction, 30% reported no change, and only 12% said their satisfaction declined. Retrospective evaluations showed an average gain of 1.5 points on a 0–10 scale, while causal modeling yielded a smaller yet still notable increase of 0.8 points, equivalent to about a 13% improvement. For comparison, previous EU migration studies (e.g., Graham & Nikolova, 2015) reported a similar 1.5-point gain, suggesting that the well-being benefits of East-to-West migration may be declining over time.

The most consistent improvements were observed in satisfaction with income and public services. In both domains, the average increase was around 2.5 points. By contrast, fewer than half of respondents reported improvement in health, social relationships, or time use. In particular, social relationships showed notable strain: 32% of respondents felt their social ties had weakened after migration. Despite this, nearly 40% experienced improvement in 6 or 7 of the 9 life domains we measured, and 11% reported gains across all areas. Just 3% indicated no improvement in any area of life.

Improvements in life satisfaction were not uniform. Migrants with lower initial satisfaction, such as those with lower educational attainment, were more likely to report positive change. Those who moved for relationship reasons showed smaller average gains, aligning with patterns seen among “trailing partners,” who often relocate without clear professional plans or with qualifications that are harder to transfer. One striking result came from recent migrants, who reported a 3-point jump in satisfaction with public services, highlighting a particularly strong contrast between Austria and Hungary in this area.

Across affective measures, retrospective assessments revealed clear shifts: positive emotions became more frequent, while negative emotions became less common. For instance, the share of people who reported feeling “mostly or always down” dropped from 23% to 5%, while those who felt “mostly or always happy” rose from 38% to 70%. However, in causal models restricted to those who migrated within the last decade, these differences were not statistically significant. One emotional domain where the improvement was not evident was loneliness. Migrants who left behind a partner or child were particularly affected. Among those having a left-behind close family member, the share who reported feeling “rarely or never lonely” remained unchanged at 55% after migrations, and half of those who reported never having felt lonely before migration now feel mostly lonely.

Almost 60% of respondents noted improved optimism, with an average change of 1 point. Causal models supported this trend, showing a statistically significant increase of 1.26 points. In the eudaimonic domain, freedom to live life as one chooses stood out as a key area of improvement, particularly among the more educated, who reported 1.5 points higher increase than migrants with primary education.

When asked whether their migration experience fulfilled their hopes, 70% of respondents said yes. However, only 26.1% felt completely satisfied, while 43.9% reported being mostly satisfied. A further 23% gave mixed responses, and only 4.5% expressed failure. 9.4% of migrants said they planned to return to Hungary within three years, double the proportion of those who had a failed migration. But only half of the potential returnees had made any concrete plans. Social ties were the most commonly cited reason for return (76%), followed by the sense that initial goals had already been met, and public safety concerns. Return intentions tended to cluster around specific profiles: those who migrated to support future plans in Hungary, had spent less time in Austria, and showed high levels of transnational engagement (e.g., frequent visits home). Returnees reported lower life satisfaction (average 6.5) than those who planned to stay, and even lower than the average of potential migrants still living in Hungary. Our model suggests that pre-migration dissatisfaction may carry over and has a connection with migration outcomes. Indeed, a 1-point drop in pre-migration satisfaction was associated with a 3% higher chance of returning.

Yet not all returnees are dissatisfied. Among those we labelled “target earners”, who moved to achieve specific financial or personal goals, the average life satisfaction increased by 2.2 points, exceeding that of those who planned to stay. Conversely, those returning for relationship reasons showed a more modest average increase of just 0.4 points.

Challenges in Finding a Better Life

“I heard about the Austro-Hungarian Empire from Austrians before I heard about it from Hungarians. They don't see us as immigrants. I see how Austrians laugh at certain other nationalities. It's interesting, but they seem to be pretty accepting of us, at least that's how I feel. So somehow, they don't really see us as immigrants.”

Man, 30–45, Cashier, in AT

This summary highlights four key challenges that can hinder the success of migration from Hungary to Austria, based on both existing literature and interviews: overqualification, language barriers, discrimination, and transnational ties.

Roughly 25–30% of Hungarians in Austria are overqualified, working in roles below their level of education. While this is only slightly above Austria's national rate (~23%), the patterns differ: among Austrians, men are more often overqualified, while in our Hungarian sample, women are 13% more likely than men to experience this mismatch. Among potential migrants still living in Hungary and planning to move to Austria, 61% would accept a job below their qualifications. While overqualification is not directly linked to overall life satisfaction (there is an indirect way however, via reduced income), it correlates with lower income expectations, reduced job satisfaction (11% lower), and higher levels of chronic stress. It also raises the risk of disappointment: migrants who are overqualified are 8% more likely to report that migration did not meet their expectations.

According to our survey, 11% of Hungarians in Austria speak only basic German, and the true figure may be higher. Lower proficiency is more common among men and recent migrants. Among potential migrants in Hungary who are planning to relocate to Austria, 68% report basic or no German skills, and 27% say they don't speak the language at all. Language skills are closely associated with social inclusion. Migrants fluent in German are 40% more likely to report no feelings of exclusion. As earlier findings showed, perceived exclusion has a strong negative effect on well-being. Low language proficiency also aligns with higher return intentions. Those with only basic German are 14% more likely to consider returning to Hungary than those with conversational skills.

Although our survey did not directly assess experiences of discrimination, interviewees shared subtle signs of exclusion. While explicit unequal treatment was rarely reported, many felt they were still seen as “foreigners”, even when fluent in German, pointing to the limits of full integration. Still, many participants said Hungarians are viewed more positively in Austria compared to other immigrant groups.

Transnational ties, maintained through visits, remittances, and emotional support, can both enrich and complicate the migration experience. Frequent visits to Hungary are common and emotionally complex. Many migrants described them as rewarding but also stressful. Several

interviewees said that trips back reinforced their decision to migrate, especially after encountering negative experiences with public services or political discourse in Hungary. There is a striking contrast in institutional trust: 80% of respondents trust the Austrian media and government more than their Hungarian counterparts. Many perceive that politics is more intrusive in Hungary.

47% of migrants provide financial or emotional support to family in Hungary. The average amount sent is €330 per month, with higher amounts reported by those planning to return. Return-planning migrants send €150 more on average, and those with a partner in Hungary send an additional €250 monthly. Remittances are more common among: those with lower education, those who visit home frequently, and those who intend to return. By contrast, migrants are less likely to send money if they've lived longer in Austria or live with their children there. Interestingly, those who send remittances, especially to close family members, also report higher satisfaction with work.

23% of respondents left behind a partner or child in Hungary. These individuals report more negative outcomes in several well-being indicators. For example, those with a partner still in Hungary are 12.6% less likely to say they are “always happy” compared to those living with their partner. Separation from loved ones appears to be one of the strongest stressors in the migration experience. While transnational connections can offer emotional grounding, they also carry burdens, financial, logistical, and emotional, that may counteract the potential well-being benefits of migration.